

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Bekarian**FIRST NAME:** Mary**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following is the most crucial step in ensuring that your essay is critically engaging and well-supported?
 - Prioritizing creative thinking over critical analysis to make the essay more unique.
 - Only including evidence that agrees with your argument to maintain consistency.
 - Evaluating differing arguments and explaining why one is more convincing than the other.¹**
 - Skimming through sources quickly and selecting only a few that confirm your initial viewpoint.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 9.

2. According to Turabian's style guide, what is a common pitfall when evaluating research questions?
- Asking a question that requires a speculative answer with no possible evidence.²**
 - Asking questions that require deep critical thinking and original analysis.
 - Focusing only on primary sources without consulting secondary sources.
 - Avoiding questions that invite multiple valid interpretations.
3. Which of the following best describes the primary purpose of a research argument and conversation with the research community in the Turabian style?
- To convince the reader by using rhetorical strategies rather than evidence.
 - To bludgeon the reader into accepting a claim through aggressive persuasion.
 - To engage in a cooperative conversation with skeptical but receptive colleagues.³**
 - To present research findings without justifying claims with reasoning.
4. In the notes-bibliography citation style, which of the following is TRUE regarding quotation marks?
- Short, direct quotations are enclosed in double quotation marks and incorporated into the text.⁴**

² Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 28.

³ Ibid., 21–22.

⁴ Ibid., 371.

- Block quotations require double quotation marks at the beginning and end.
 - Parenthetical citations are required for every quotation, regardless of placement.
 - Single quotation marks should be used for all quotations in Turabian style.
5. Which of the following is NOT a source of researcher bias in dissertation research?
- Random selection of participants from a diverse population.**⁵
 - Selecting research questions to satisfy an ulterior motive.
 - Selectively including or excluding portions of professional literature.
 - Emphasizing specific discussion points to align with a predetermined conclusion.
6. According to Sampson, what is the primary reason for structuring a dissertation into four distinct components (concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript)?
- To make the dissertation process longer and more complex.
 - To satisfy the requirements of most universities for graduation.
 - To allow for a step-by-step refinement of research ideas and methodologies.**⁶
 - To ensure that the research remains strictly qualitative or quantitative.
7. Why does Sampson emphasize the inclusion of the research setting in the dissertation title?
- To provide a detailed description of the institution where the research took place.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research, Second Edition*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 8–9.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 2–5.

- To acknowledge the influence of the setting on research findings and their generalizability.⁷**
- Because APA formatting requires all dissertation titles to include the research location.
- To ensure the reader knows exactly where the researcher was physically present.
8. According to the WHO Style Guide, which naming convention statement is correct?
- Use “North Korea” instead of “Democratic People's Republic of Korea” to maintain brevity.
- WHO allows internal acronyms like "HQ" and "WPRO" in external documents for consistency.
- When referring to WHO Member States, always use the official UN-recognized country names.⁸**
- The acronym "WHA" should always be used instead of "World Health Assembly" to prevent confusion.
9. According to the WHO Style Guide, what is the correct approach when introducing an abbreviation in a document?
- Define the abbreviation only in footnotes to keep the main text concise.
- Introduce the term in full only once in the document.

⁷ Sampson, 24–25.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*, 2nd ed. (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 5–7.

- Before using it throughout the document, introduce the full term first, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses.⁹**
- Apply WHO requires abbreviations to be capitalized even if their full form is in lowercase.

10. Which of the following is an incorrect use of capitalization according to WHO style?

- WHO Regional Office for Europe.
- WHO Collaborating Centre for Nursing Development.
- WHO Member nations.¹⁰**
- World Health Organization.

⁹ World Health Organization, 19.

¹⁰ Ibid., 5.

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